

OUR VISION FOR A EUROPEAN eDNA DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM

Aquatic environmental DNA (eDNA) holds enormous potential for biodiversity research and monitoring, contributing to the development of effective policy and regulatory frameworks. However, this potential has yet to be realised.

eDNAqua-Plan is developing a roadmap to guide the transition from the current fragmented and sub-optimal digital landscape to a vision of a more harmonised, interoperable, and sustainable ecosystem, based on FAIR data practices. This future landscape will support the implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the Water Framework Directive and help us achieve the goals of the EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters, and the EU Green Deal.

The Vision

- Increased adoption of interoperable standards and widely used web-technologies
- Expansion of minimum collected metadata
- A network of connected, searchable and reliable reference libraries
- Federation, not centralisation: Building on what exists
- Better resourced data management
- Quality label for databases and libraries implementing best practices
- Incentivised community participation (acknowledgements and data attributions)
- Local action in a global context

The Roadmap

Short term

- Support operationalisation of DNA-based use cases for WFD & MSFD implementation
- Advance CEN / ISO standards, link with TDWG/GSC and maintain mappings
- Complete reference databases
- Set up a consortium to finalise the checklist of essential metadata for curated reference libraries, mapping these to existing standards and vocabularies
- Encourage systematic data deposition in INSDC / ENA
- Encourage the roll out of FAIRe to implementers

Medium term

- Federated infrastructure and search engine to connect reference libraries and query their (meta)data
- End-to-end analytical & FAIR data publishing pipelines
- Formal intercalibration between monitoring methods
- DNA-specific indicators for MSFD
- Training and capacity building (methods & data)
- Sustainable funding for repositories, databases and infrastructure

Find reports, resources and provide your feedback
ednaqua-plan.com/join-involved

Funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme, Grant Agreement No. 101112800 (eDNAqua-Plan). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

